

Resonance Enhanced Multiphoton Ionization Detection of Vibrationally Excited O₂

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Figure S1. Measured two-color ($2 + 1'$) resonance-enhanced multiphoton ionization (REMPI) spectra of the relatively isolated $3d\pi^3\Sigma_g^+(0) (v' = 0) \leftarrow X^3\Sigma_g^-(v' = 0, 1)$ Rydberg transitions of O_2 compared to labelled PGOPHER⁴⁸ simulations. The top panel (a) shows experimental data (blue trace) taken without the silicon carbide (SiC) tube agree with a 10 K simulation (black trace). The green trace in the second panel (b) was taken with the SiC tube; the red and magenta traces are 5 and 25 K simulations, respectively, with the black trace showing their sum. The orange trace in the bottom panel (c) is taken with the SiC tube heated to 1000 K; the dark teal and bright green traces are 150 and 500 K simulations, respectively, with the black trace as their sum. Spectra recorded using the SiC tube cannot be well recreated using a single temperature. However, using two temperatures improves the agreement significantly. The feature marked by an asterisk is the $J'' = J' = 0$ transitions, which can be accounted for by a small amount of very cold gas (~ 5 K) – this recurs in most electronic bands.

Figure S2. Measured two-color ($2 + 1'$) resonance-enhanced multiphoton ionization (REMPI) spectra of the $3d\pi \ ^3\Sigma_g^-(0) (v' = 0) \leftarrow X \ ^3\Sigma_g^- (v' = 0)$ Rydberg transition of O_2 (black trace) compared to PGOPHER⁴⁸ simulations (blue, red, and green traces) with increasing values of the upper state spin-spin coupling constant (λ_{s-s}). The λ_{s-s} signs are consistent with the $^3\Sigma_g^-$ states lying below the $^3\Sigma_g^+$ states.³⁷ The values were set empirically, predominantly based on the best fit to the cold spectra, where the electronic bands are better separated.